

ABU'L FAZL'S PREFACE TO THE PERSIAN TRANSLATION OF THE MAHABHARAT

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Abu'l Fazl's preface to the Persian translation of the *Mahabharat* is an extremely valuable source for the study of Akbar's religious policy, though unfortunately it has not attracted the attention that it deserves. In this preface, Abu'l Fazl explains Akbar's desire to bring about a positive understanding between Hindus and the Muslims and the reason why Akbar established a translation bureau for getting Sanskrit works translated into Persian.

Akbar ordered Naqīb Khān¹ to prepare a translation of the *Mahabharat* in collaboration with Mulla 'Abdul Qādir Badāunī and Shaikh Ḥājī Sultān Thānesarī.² A number of Hindu scholars were asked to explain the work to the translators who were ordered to render it into Persian. According to the colophon³ of the manuscript of the *Mahabharat* no. *Tārīkh*, *Lytton Library, Aligarh University*, these Hindu scholars were Debi Misr, Satuwani, Madhsudhan Misr, Chaturbhuj Misr and Shaikh Bhawan.⁴ According to

1. Naqīb Khān, son of Mir 'Abdul Laṭīf of Qazwīn, arrived with his father in India, when Akbar after his accession had not yet left the Punjab, (*Akbar Nāma*, Bib. Ind., Vol. II, p. 230) and soon became a personal friend of the emperor. (*Akbar Nāma*, II, p. 281). He generally read out the books to the emperor and supervised the translation of Sanskrit works into Persian. He also wrote several sections of *Tārīkh-i-Alfī* (Ethe, India Office Manuscripts, 112). He excelled in historiography and was said to have committed all the seven volumes of *Rauzat-us-Ṣāfa* (a general history in seven volumes, from the creation down to 929H/1522-23, by Muḥammad ibn Khāwand Shāh ibn Mahmud, known as Mīr-Khwand, Browne Persian Catalogue, 44-56), to memory. According to Mulla 'Abdul Qādir Badāunī, no man in Arabic or Persian was as proficient in History as Naqīb Khan. Jahangīr also very highly extolled the virtues of Naqīb Khan as a scholar. He died in 1023H/1614.

2. Ḥājī Sultān Thānesarī remained in the service of Akbar for a long time. According to Badāunī, he was banished from Thānesar on account of the accusation of the crime of cow killing brought against him by the Hindus of that Pargana, but was after some time pardoned owing to the intercession of Khan-i-Khanan and was appointed *Karori* of Thānesar and Karnāl. He appeared to have continued and completed the translation of the *Mahābhārat*. On being asked, when he was translating the *Mahābhārat*, the question what he was writing, he replied, "I am translating what was well known ten thousand years ago into the modern tongue." (Badāunī, *Muntakhab-ut-Tawārīkh*, Vol. III, Bib. Ind., pp. 118-119)

3. The present manuscript was transcribed by one 'Abdur Raḥmān in Kashmir who mentions the date of transcription to be 1112H/1700-1 in words and 1013H/1604-5 in figures.

قد فرغت من تسويد هذا الكتاب بحسب الامر على حضرت خلائف نهائي - العبد بنده فقير الحقير... عبدالرحمن
في بلدة الكشمير همت تحرير يافت - سده اثناء عشر و الف و صاية في يوم - شهر ربيع الاول سنة 1113 هـ

1 hundred in words appears to be an oversight of the copyist, because the title-page of the manuscript contains an autograph dated 1048H/1638. *Khilāfat Panāhi* also appears to have been used for Akbar, because Aurangzeb cannot be said to have been interested in the transcription of the *Mahābhārat*. Moreover, he was busy in that year in the conquest of Deccan and so he could not possibly order an inhabitant of Kashmir to transcribe the *Mahābhārat*. Lastly the title *Khilāfat Panāhi* has also been used for Akbar by Naqīb Khān.

4. The name of the Hindu scholars who collaborated the translations of *Mahābhārat* except Shaikh Bhāwan, a learned Brahman of Deccan who was afterwards converted to Islam, and translated a portion of the *Atharva Veda* (Badāunī, II, 213) is nowhere available in the colophon of the Lyton Library manuscript.

Badāunī, Faizi and Mulla Shīrī⁵ also took part in the work of translation.⁶ A portion of the translation in which Naqīb Khān played the most prominent part was completed within one and a half years on Monday, the 27th Sh'abān, 992H/September 4, 1584.⁷ It was finally completed by Sulṭān Ḥājī Thānesarī in the 32nd solar year of Akbar's reign, i.e., 1587-88.⁸

Akbar took a keen interest in the work and supervised it personally. Badāunī writes that for several nights he himself heard the Brahmans interpret the *Mahabharat* and explained its meaning to Naqīb Khān. Akbar also expressed a desire that the work be given wide publicity and the nobles were ordered to get copies transcribed for themselves.

The preface of the translation was written by Shaikh Abu'l Fazl. Badāunī writes, "Shaikh Abu'l Fazl, as against the commentary on the Āyat-al-Kursī,⁹ which he had formerly composed, now wrote for it (*Mahabharat*) a preface extending to two (*Juz*)."¹⁰ Since there is no apparent contradiction between Abu'l Fazl's commentary on the Qurānic verse, Āyat-al-Kursī, and the present preface, and as Abu'l Fazl does not in any way refer to the commentary, Badāunī apparently intended to convey the impression that whereas the former work which was presented by Abu'l Fazl to Akbar in 1574¹¹ was written as a good Muslim, the latter work was written as an unbeliever.

The preface may be found in many of the extant manuscripts of *Mahabharat*, as well as in the lithographed edition of the *Nawal Kishore Press*. It runs into twenty folios of the *Aligarh manuscript*¹² and consists of two parts: (a) Akbar's motives in getting the work translated (Ff. 1a-10b), (b) a summary of the main problems discussed in the Persian translation of the *Mahabharat*, Ff. 10b-20b.

5. Mulla Shīrī, the son of Maulāna Yahyā, was a very good poet. He died in the campaign against Yusufza'īs in which Raja Bir Bar was killed (994H/1586). (Bad, III, pp. 249-252).

6. Bad, II, p. 320.

7.

تمام شد کتاب مہابھارت بحمد اللہ تعالیٰ و حسن ترقیتہ و بمن توجہ حضرت خلافت پناہی سلطان جاہی
سکندر نشانی خاد ملکہ و سلطانہ و افامس علی العالمین برہ و احسانہ

روز در شنبہ بست و ہفتم ماہ شعبان المعظم سنہ اثنی و تسعین و تسعمایہ

8. Preface to the *Mahābhārat*, f. 8b, (*Abdus Salam Manuscripts* No. 450/5) ; Life of Ḥājī Sulṭān Thānesarī ; where Badāunī says that Ḥājī worked for four years in order to complete the translation started by Naqīb Khān. (Bad, III, p. 118). In the second volume of *Muntakhab-ut-Tawārikh*, i.e., History of Akbar) the whole event is placed in the twenty-eighth year of Akbar's reign, but later, however, he says, "The author begs leave to request, that the reader will excuse him if in the account of this year (which has been introduced as a digression, written down by his rapid pen in an abridged form) he has not observed a strictly chronological order, nor preserved the exact sequence of events". (Bad, II, p. 321).

9. A verse from Quran.

10.

شیخ ابو الفضل بر عکس تفسیر آیة الکرسی کہ تالیف دادہ بود خطبہ نیز بمقدار در جزو بران نوشت
نعوذ باللہ من الکفریات و العشویات -

11. *Akbar Nāmā*, (Bib. Ind.) III, p. 85, Bad, II, p. 198.

12. *'Abdus-Salām Manuscripts*, 450/5.

The preface opens with the words Śrī Gaṇeśāya namaḥ¹³ (श्रीगणेशाय नमः). Then follows the praise and supplication to God in the same style as the doxology in his *Munājāt*.¹⁴

Before discussing Akbar's motives in getting works of different languages translated into Persian, Abu'l Faḥl laments that the rulers in the past neglected the most important duty of looking after the religious needs of the common people. Even when the religious problems of the common people reached the ears of the rulers in the past, they did not pay any heed to such matters. Being afraid of a campaign of slander which "babblers" might have started against them if they dared take up religious questions themselves, these rulers entrusted these to the people who did not know anything except issuing *Fatwas* (religious decrees) and to the theologians (who failed to understand the real significance of religion).¹⁵

But, says Abu'l Faḥl, Akbar initiated a bold policy so that in his age "the pillars of blind following" were demolished and a new era of research and enquiry (in religious matters) started.¹⁶ Referring to the new regulations and ordinances which were issued on religious subjects, he says that after they were promulgated, people found it difficult to imagine how the kings in the past were able to rule without them.¹⁷ Then follows an examination of the inventions of Akbar and a reference to some of his other institutes and sayings, including his ideas in respect of abstaining from taking meat for about seven months in a year and his views in opposition to non-vegetarianism.¹⁸

After extolling the virtues of the Emperor, Abu'l Faḥl discusses the motives of Akbar in getting the *Mahābhārat* translated into Persian. He says that Akbar was anxious to introduce reforms among all classes of his subjects and did not discriminate between a friend or a foe. As he found that there were exceedingly great differences amongst Hindus and Muslims, and there was no end to the polemics and refutations of each other, he decided to get the reliable books of both the religions translated in the language of their opponents, so that shaking off their enmity¹⁹ they should try to search for truth. However having been acquainted with their respective weaknesses, they should try to reform themselves.

Secondly in every religion there were a number of ignorant ones who always thought themselves to be great scholars and misrepresented the original

13. One of the Hindu forms of beginning a work employing thereby "We perform a salute to the god Gaṇeśa (गणेश)". Abu'l Faḥl similarly begins the translation of the Bible with the words *اے نام دے ژژو کرسٹو* (Thou whose name is Jesus Christ, i.e., Saviour and Anointed). Badāunī however translated the words as *اے آنکه نان و و مہبارتم بسیار بخش است* (O, Thou whose name is merciful and very bountiful).

14. *Munājāt* is *Manṭuqā'* (Expression) I of *Latāif-i-Faiḥlī*, a collection of letters of Shaikh Faizī, compiled by his sister's son Nuruddin Muhammad in 1035H/1625-26. (Lyton Supp. *Farsiya Akhbār*, 51) ff 84b-101a. It is being published in the *Medieval India Quarterly* (Vol. I, No. 3). For a reference.

15. Preface to the *Mahābhārat*, 'Abdus Salam Mss., 450/5 ff. 2a-2b.

16. *Ibid*, f. 3a.

17. Preface to the *Mahābhārat*, 'Abdus Salam Mss., 450/5, f. 4a.

18. *Ibid*, f. 8a. All these points are discussed at length in *Āin-i-Akbari*.

19. *Ibid*, f. 9b.

works of the Masters. Common people mistook these misrepresentations for the real religion and were often misled. Akbar thought it essential to protect the people from becoming a victim to the nefarious designs of such custodians of faith and came to the decision that if the books of different religions could be translated into a simple language, the common people would be able to know the truth for themselves.²⁰

The "*Mahabharat*", continues Abu'l Fazl, "which is the work of the sages of India, and greater than which is no book of their faith, was ordered to be translated. Many of the leaders of the faith among Hindus, in their bigotry and incapacity to see truth, have an exaggerated and blind faith in their beliefs. On account of their inability to see truth and justice they regard even the details of their religion as being above question, and follow the faith blindly. They have so impressed upon the common undiscerning folk, certain articles of faith, that these are accepted without question or an inquiry.

"Muslims who are ignorant of the subtlety and sublimity of the religion of Hindus, basing their judgment on the beliefs of the above (*i.e.*, common misrepresentation of the Hindu faith) bitterly refute Hinduism. It was therefore decided that the *Mahabharat* be translated so that those who refute them may give up their prejudiced opposition, and the uncritical believers may be enabled to seek truth.

"The common Muslims who have not studied the heavenly and other books of religion, nor have any insight in the history of different peoples such as the Chinese and the Indians etc., nor have studied the works of great men of their own religion like Imām J'āfar-i-Şādiq²¹ and Ibn-al-'Arabī²² believe that the human race has been in existence for seven thousand years and all the intellectual heritage of the human race is the contribution of these seven thousand years. Therefore it was decided that the *Mahabharat* which dealt with the great antiquity of the world and its people and bears witness to the much older age of the world and its inhabitants, be translated in simple language, so that the people (*i.e.*, such Muslims) may give up their improper belief. Let it be known that finer knowledge and nobler comprehension are without a beginning and these jewels of wisdom have no origin."²³

Lastly, concludes Abu'l Fazl, the study of history was very popular among all types of people and particularly among the kings. "The divine mysteries contained in history served as an example to the people." It also enabled the people to "improve the present in the light of the past, hence the translation of the *Mahabharat* was given priority for it also comprised the ancient history of India."

20. *Ibid*, f. 9b.

21. He was the eldest son of Muhammad Bāqir, and the sixth Imam of the Shi'as. He was born at Madīnah about the year 702 A.D. and died in 765 A.D. He was very famous among his contemporaries for his learning and scholarship. Many Sunni Jurists were his disciples. None of his works are extant, yet he is known to have written many standard works on Shi'a theology.

22. Shaikh Muḥī'-ud-Din Abu 'Abdullāh ibn Muhammad ibn Alī aṭ-Ṭai-al-Haṭimi-al-Andalusi, was the author of two extremely well known treatises on Pantheistic mysticism, viz. *Fusūs-ul-Hakam* and *Fatuhāt-i-Makkia*. He died in 1240 A.D.

23.

و این جواهر دانش را مبدی منه

The preface also deals with the scheme of translation. It shows that Akbar earnestly desired that the translation should be as faithful as possible.²⁴ Scholars of both the religions who were expert in their respective languages were recruited to translate the work with their mutual consultation and "consent". It was essential for the scholars that they should be scrupulously honest in their work and should keep themselves aloof from bigotry.²⁵

The rest of the preface (ff. 10b-20b) contains a brief summary of the *Mahabharat* and the various problems discussed in the work. This summary provides further testimony to Abu'l Fazl's erudition and deep scholarship. He has surveyed the work objectively but sympathetically, and has successfully tried to catch its spirit.

Importance of Preface: Akbar's motives in getting the Sanskrit works translated into Persian, have been discussed by Mulla 'Abdul Qādir Badāunī at length. He says, that after getting *Shah Nama* and the *story of Amir Hamza* transcribed and having heard the *stories of Abu Muslim* and the *Jami-ul-Hikayat*, he decided to get the works of the ancient Indian sages translated into Persian. He thought to himself, "Why should not I have them done in my name, for they are by no means trite, but quite fresh, and they will produce all kinds of felicity both temporal and spiritual, and will be the cause of circumstance and pomp, and will ensure an abundance of children and wealth, as is written in the preface of these books." But the preface of the *Mahabharat* is the first documentary evidence of the real motives of Akbar in establishing a sort of "translation bureau" which aimed at achieving something higher in comparison with the translation bureau of Mamūn-ur-Rashīd, the seventh Abbasid Caliph (813 A.D.-884 A.D.). While Mamūn was actuated only by intellectual curiosity, Akbar's motives were both intellectual and practical. It was for the betterment of the members of both the communities that the work was undertaken and did not mean any hostility to Islam, as it has been frequently represented by Badāunī. The causes of the discouragement, which religious chauvinism received in the reign of Akbar are nowhere better explained than in the present preface. The policy of "peace with all" was not merely a philosophical abstraction with either Akbar or Abu'l Fazl, but both of them tried to bring about a positive understanding between the members of both the communities. The preface shows, how Akbar himself tried to understand the very spirit of Hinduism and earnestly desired that others should also do the same.

24. In the translation of the Atharva Veda, Shaikh Bhawan tried to prove that it contained many sentences similar to "La Ilaha Ilallah". (Bad, II, p. 213.) Apparently the forgeries of Shaikh Bhawan were exposed and the attempt to get it translated was given up. Akbar, as we have seen, personally supervised the translation of the *Mahābhārat*, and "the work was brought to such a point of perfection that not a flymark of the original was omitted". (Badāunī II, p. 321.) From another statement of Badāunī at the end of the work, it appears that Akbar had a suspicion that Badāunī tried to misinterpret the portions of the *Mahābhārat* assigned to him for translation. (Bad, II, pp. 399-400.)

25. Preface to the *Mahābhārat*, Op. Cit f. 10a.